

Table 1. Yield and income from rice - fish farming system. Hunan, China, 1990-91.

Farming system	Yield (t/ha)			Gross return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
	Rice	Rape	Fish			
Rice - rape (control)	13.8	1.2		2068.9	1145.0	1.24
Rice - azolla - rape	14.2	1.2		2119.2	1167.9	1.21
Rice - azolla - fish - rape	12.9	1.2	0.5	2490.8	1501.1	1.52

Table 2. Energy transformation of rice - fish farming system. Hunan, China, 1990-91.

	Rice - rape (control)	Rice - azolla - rape	Rice - azolla - fish - rape
<i>Energy input (10⁸J/ha)</i>			
Total	2274	2647.0	2739
Organic	1594	1984	2082
Inorganic	268	260	252
Commodity	413	404	404
<i>Energy output (10⁸J/ha)</i>			
Total	3774.1	4647	4626
Product	2119.9	2182.4	2092
Secondary product			69
By-product	1654.2	2465	2465
<i>Energy efficiency</i>			
Output:input	1.66	1.76	1.69
Product:inorganic	7.92	8.40	8.29
Product:commodity	5.14	5.41	5.17
Inorganic:input	0.12	0.10	0.09
Light use efficiency (%)	1.03	1.23	1.21

Productivity of rainfed rice-based cropping systems in West Bengal

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We studied the relative productivity of summer crops and their effect on wet

season (WS) rice and their residual effect on lentil *Lens culinaris* L. The rice-based cropping systems were evaluated under rainfed conditions in the subhumid tropics during 1989-91.

The soil was clayey loam with pH 6.8, 0.61% organic C, 0.062% total N, 15 kg available P, and 160 kg available K/ha.

WS rice fertilized with 0, 50, or 100 kg N/ha was transplanted after the

Effect of crops and N level on wet rice yields^a and aftereffect on lentil under rainfed condition. West Bengal, India, 1989-91.

Treatment ^b	Crop yield (t/ha)						Total		Net returns (US\$ha)
	1st crop		2d crop (rice)		3d crop (lentil)				
	Grain/fiber	Straw/stock	Grain	Straw	Grain	Stock	Grain/fiber	Straw/stock	
<i>Cropping system</i>									
Fallow - rice - lentil	0.0	0.0	1.7	2.0	1.4	2.6	3.1	4.6	312
Jute - rice - lentil	1.8	8.1	3.2	3.7	1.6	2.8	6.6	14.6	1212
Rice (d) - rice - lentil	2.5	2.7	1.6	1.8	1.3	2.3	5.4	6.8	816
Mungbean - rice - lentil	0.8	7.8	3.2	3.7	1.5	2.6	5.5	14.1	980
Sesame - rice - lentil	0.9	9.1	1.6	1.7	1.4	2.4	3.9	13.2	644
Mean	1.2	5.5	2.3	2.6	1.4	2.5	4.9	10.7	—
LSD (0.05)	0.2	1.4	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	—	—	—
<i>N level in rice (kg/ha)</i>									
0	—	—	2.0	2.4	1.4	2.4	3.4	4.8	376
50	—	—	2.3	2.5	1.4	2.6	3.7	5.1	440
100	—	—	2.6	2.9	1.5	2.6	4.1	5.5	528
Mean	—	—	2.3	2.6	1.4	2.5	3.7	5.1	—
LSD (0.05)	—	—	2.0	0.1	ns	ns	—	—	—

^aMean of 2 yr. ns = not significant. ^bRice (d) = direct seeded rice.

benefit-cost ratio. Gross return, net return, and benefit-cost ratio were highest in the rice - azolla - fish - rape farming system.

Rice - azolla - rape gave the highest energy output, output-input energy ratio, product energy-inorganic energy ratio, product energy-commodity energy ratio, and light use efficiency (Table 2). Inorganic energy-input energy ratio was lowest in rice - azolla - fish - rape system. □

harvest of a fallow check and four upland crops: jute cultivar Basudev, direct seeded rice MW 10, mungbean cultivar Pusa Baisakhi, and sesame cultivar Tilottama. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design on 8- × 2-m plots.

All summer crops were sown 2 May and harvested 31 Jul; IR36 rice was transplanted 7 Aug (25 d after seeding) at 25- × 25-cm spacing, with 4 seedlings/hill. K and P (25 kg/ha each) were applied to the rice, which was harvested 14 Nov. Lentil (B77) was broadcast 19 Nov and harvested 28 Feb. No fertilizer was used.

Grain and straw yields of rice were maximum after either jute or mungbean (see table). Results were similar for third-crop lentil grain and stock yields. Jute - rice - lentil showed the maximum crop production and net return among the 3-crop systems. The mungbean - rice - lentil sequence was second.

Grain and straw/stock yields of both rice and lentil increased as the N level increased. Net returns of rice also increased. □

Farm machinery

Development of spinning brush VLV pesticide applicator

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The spinning brush very low volume (VLV) pesticide applicator is a new low-cost system that reduces labor. It works on the principle that when the bristles of